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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarc@gmail.com

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jichelnu@gmail.com

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A Study on the Separate Legal Identities of the Jains

Dr. Anindya Bandyopadhyay¹

Abstract

The Jains are about four million in Indian subcontinent. Similar to the Buddhists, it is evolved in the Gangetic plains during the sixth and seventh century BCE. Like Buddhism, Jainism is also a monastic religion which denies the authority of the Veda; as a result, the Brāhmaṇas regarded it as a heretical. Buddhism has stretched its branches throughout south-eastern and eastern Asia, Jainism, on the other hand, has never ever left the Indian main land and they amalgamated with the “Hindus” with their separate ideas, theologies and definitely with their identities. The colonial scholars had a complicated idea about Jain communities. They never identified the Jains *as an independent religious sect before the publishing of Kalpasūtra of Bhadrabāhu by Professor Jacobi, a well-known colonial scholar. After publication of Jacobi’s work, Jainism became gradually recognized as a universal or ‘world religion’*. This paper discusses the similarities and the dissimilarities between the Jain law and the law of Brahmanical dharmasāstras. This study argues on the separate legal identities of the Jains following their own legal texts and the medieval Jain literature. This study will enrich and expand existing knowledge of Indian legal chronicles, unobserved by the earlier scholars.

Approximately four million Jains live on the Indian subcontinent today. It developed in the Gangetic plain during the sixth and seventh centuries BCE, similar to the Buddhists. Like Buddhism, Jainism is also a monastic religion that denies the authority of the Vedas; as a result, the Brāhmaṇas regarded it as a heretical. Buddhism has stretched its branches throughout south-eastern and eastern Asia,

1. *Head, Department of Sanskrit, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia , West Bengal, India*

Jainism, on the other hand, has never ever left the Indian main land and they amalgamated with the so-called Hindus into different parts of Indian sub-continent with their separate ideas, theologies and definitely with their identities.²

Theoretically, though the Jains eschew Vedic ritualistic portions, in reality, they have incorporated most of the Vedic philosophical ideas into their own theosophical framework. Likewise, the Buddhist, the Jains have also grafted various Brahmanical theosophical ideas too into their own monastic tradition, viz. 1) karman (the supremacy of moral order), 2) saṃsāra (the concept of cyclical rebirth), and 3) mokṣa (the innate capacity of human beings to escape the cycle). Their smooth blending with the Brahmanical tradition, the Jains, therefore, have not been regarded by the leading Brahmanical philosophical texts as their intellectual adversaries (pūrvapakṣin) like the Buddhists and the Cārvākas. The colonial scholars, therefore, in the very beginning, have a complicated idea relating to the Jain communities. They had not identified the Jains as an independent religious sect like the Hindus, before publishing the book namely *Kalpasūtra of Bhadrabāhu* in 1879. The reason is simple. If we move from the level of intellectuals to the level of a day-to-day life of many traditional Hindus, we find that they hardly consider the Jains and the Buddhists to be individual sects different from the so-called Hindu community. For instance, the injunction imposed on the non-Hindus not to be able to enter the orthodox Hindu temples like Jagannatha or other places should not be regarded as conclusive against the general perception of both the Jains and Buddhists.³

The Colonial scholars, for the first time, discovered the Jains as an individual sect after the publication of the book *Kalpasūtra of Bhadrabāhu* by Hermann Jacobi. In the introduction of his edition, he points out that the ancient Hindus and the Buddhist scriptures have already identified the Jain as a separate heretical group, describing themselves as a nigganthas (knot-less). Prior to this observation of

2 See 'Distribution of Population by Religions', Drop-in-Article on Census - No.4: Census of India 2011.

3 I should express my personal thanks to B.K.Swain, Professor of dharmaśāstra, Śrī Jagannath University, Puri, Odhisha, for providing me the whereabouts relating to the Jagannath Temple. Traditionally, the Jains, the Buddhists, the Shikhs as well as the Vaiṣṇavas, Śaivas and the Lingayats are regarded as a Hindu and they are allowed to enter into the Jagannath Temple.

Professor Jacobi, colonial scholars identify the Jain as a ‘Buddhists’ or as a ‘Hindu’ sect. After publication of Jacobi’s work, Jainism became gradually recognized as a universal or ‘world religion’. Flügel (2005:2-3), in this connection, argues, “[t]he political value of the academic study of Jainism, and Jacobi’s findings in particular, was instantly realized by the educated Jain elite, who for some time demanded the public recognition of ‘Jainism’ and the ‘Jainas’ form the colonial government and in the courts.” From the mid of the 19th century onwards most of the British educated Jain reformers started to campaign for creating a communal self-awareness amongst the Jains and considered themselves a distinct community different from the Buddhists and the Hindus. As a result, officially, the category of ‘Jain’ was introduced first time in the Census of India of 1881. It is noteworthy that during the time of Census, a number of Jain families still identified themselves with the so-called Hindu Community (ibid., 5). The issue at stake becomes what would be the legal status of the Jains? The doctrinal dissimilarities between ‘Hinduism’ and ‘Jainism’ have been recognized from the landmark judgment of Goteppa v. Eramma AIR 1972 Madras 228, where the verdict suggested that the ‘Jaina Law’ would be incorporated into the purview of ‘Hindu Law’ and the Jains would be treated as the ‘Hindus’ by the Indian Government. The aftermath of this judgment has generated the never-ending controversies why the Jain would be regarded as the Hindu. Some Nationalists like Jain advocate C. R. Jaini (1926: 7f) appropriately challenged the ambiguous legal definition of the Hindu and argues,

“[i]f a Hindu be defined as one born in India, or at the best one born in India and who was not a Mohamedan or Christian by birth then certainly every Jaina is a Hindu..... Some say Hindu is one from whom injury (Him-sa) is removed (Du-r). If this is so, only Jainas are the First and the best Hindus; whereas meat eating, hunting Hindus will not be Hindus at all. Other say, - a Hindu is one who owes allegiance to the Vedas or the Brahman. There again Jainas are not Hindus. Really it is an idle and futile problem. It all depends on what you mean by a Hindu. Let the Hindus agree upon one universal definition of a Hindu, and then it would be easy to answer the question whether a Jaina is a Hindu.”

The question remains unsettled still today and the publication of Hari Singh Gaur’s The Hindu Code in 1919 identifies the Jains as a ‘Hindu Dissenters’. Barristers J. L. Jaini (1921:8), however,

refuted the ‘misrepresentations’ of Jainism in Gaur’s Hindu Code and argues, “Dr. Gaur has erred in not distinguishing between caste and religion” and also added “[f]urther the assumption that Hindu Law applies to Jainas is absolutely illegal, as it is against statute law.”⁴ Though the elite Jains always try to identify themselves as the Jains, belonging to a separate religious code other than the Hindus, the National Commission of Minorities Act of 1992 not yet identified the Jains as a ‘minority’. Though some of the states in India, like Chattisgarh, Delhi, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh have recognized the Jains as a minority, the Government is yet to provide the minority status to the Jain community at National level.

It is true that now-a-days in world politics, self-identity is an important issue. The Jains’ demand for the minority status is about a century old demand. When in British India, the Viceroy decided that the Government would give representation to “Important Minorities” in the Legislative Council, (Petition dt. 2nd September, 1909). Seth Manekchand Hirachand, the acting President of Bharatvarshiya Digambar Jain Mahasabha during that time, appealed to the Viceroy and Governor-General of India, Lord Minto, for the inclusion of the Jain community as an important Minority. The Viceroy responded positively to this petition informing that in giving representation to minorities by nomination the claim of the important Jain community will receive full consideration. However, the problem has not yet been properly solved, because the Jains have not yet been recognized legally and separately other than a Hindu sect.

Therefore, in the present circumstances, it would be an obvious query before the academicians like us, what would be the actual legal status of the Jains for their separate identities? For the answer, we have to inquire their ancient and mediaeval legal literatures for the sake of their separate personal laws. In traditional Hindu system, the *dharmasūtras* and the *dharmasāstras* can be enumerated in this category, where directions on royal administrations and judicial processes are included. The Jains have also provided a good number of texts on religious matter, especially on monastic laws, but the texts

4 See Flügel (2007:9), vide also J. L. Jaini’s 1921 pamphlet; also, Sir William Jones on 19th March 1788 in *Digest of Hindu Law by Colebrooke*, in preface pp. v-vi; Sir M. E. Smith in 4 *Calcutta (Indian Law Reports)* at P. 751.

on king's authority or judicial administration and personal laws are scanty in number. The primary sources of Jaina law are the Prākṛta Śvetāmbara and Digambara canonical scriptures, branded as āgama or *siddhānta* including their all-embracing commentaries and annotations. The primitive 'Jain law', however, is devoted solely to the monastic jurisprudence, which still evolves through its commentary and subsidiary rules, unrestrained by the territorial interference. Śvetāmbara monastic jurisprudence combines general principles (*dharma*) i.e., five fundamental qualities (*mūla-guṇa*) and ten or more additional qualities (*uttara-guṇa*) with specific rules (*kalpa*) of good conduct (*ācāra*), supplemented by lists of common transgressions (*anācāra* or *pratisēvanā*) and corresponding atonements or penances (*prāyaścitta*). Penances are generally imposed by the head of the monastic institution (*ācārya*) as a form of punishment. The Digambaras, in contrast, have never ever developed any organized monastic order and they only follow a couple of undeveloped literatures on monastic jurisprudence. The Digambaras, therefore, regard the *Caranānuyoga* texts as authoritative for their monastic jurisprudence. *Viyāhapannatti*, the fifth *aṅga* of the Śvetāmbara Jaina canonical text, however, records four-fold communities (*tīrtha* or *saṅgha*) of the *upāsakas* (supporters) i.e. a) *sādhus* (or monks), b) *sādhvīs* (or nun), c) *śrāvakas* (or laymen) and d) *śrāvīkās* (or laywomen). Among them, Flügel argues (cf. 2005:11f.) the 'laity' is included into the religious community not earlier than the late canonical period, where first time the word *cāuvvaṇṇ* 'āiṇṇa samaṇa-saṅgha, i.e., fourfold community is recorded (cf. *Viyāhapannatti*, 792b).

The code of conduct of the laity are recorded primarily into the *śrāvakācāras* (or the treatises containing rules of conduct [ācāra] for the laity or the *śrāvakas*) and the *nītisāstras* (the texts on statecraft, law and ethics). According to the Digambaras tradition though the original *śrāvakācāra* or the *upāsakādhyayana*, lessons for the layman are lost, the Śvetambaras are able to preserve the original *Uvāsagadasāo*, the only canonical text solely devoted to the laity. The text on *śrāvakācāras* and the texts of *nītisāstras* of the Jains are the similar to the *dharmaśāstras* of the Hindus. In the later period, several legal texts and treatises on politics have been produced under

various titles to make a complete code for the Jain laity (cf. C. R. Jain, 1926). Amongst those various texts Ādipurāṇa of Ācārya **Jinasena** (ca. 770-850 CE), *Nītivākyāmr̥tam* (ca. 950 CE) and *Yaśastilaka* (959 CE) of Ācārya **Somadeva Sūri** are important Jain works on statecrafts. Though the text Ādipurāṇa deals with the legend of the first Jain ford-maker (better to say ‘law-maker’) Ṛṣava, the legal discussions, therefore recorded here are merely occasional as well as incidental. On the other hand, *Yaśastilaka* is one of the well-known Campukāvya. Therefore, the legal directives are available here is also occasional. *Nītivākyāmr̥tam*, in contrast, is an entirely secular text on statecraft modeled on the Ārthaśāstra of Kauṭilya (ca. 3rd Century BCE – 1st Century CE) with barely noticeable emphasis on the Jain morality. Other than those texts there remain two more texts which primarily deal with the code of conduct of the Jain laity. Amongst those, *Yogaśāstra and its self-made commentary of Hemacandra* (12th century CE) is the most influential medieval Śvetāmbara works concerning the Jain laity. The other one is Ācāradinakara of **Vardhamānasūri** (1411 CE), which is the first Śvetāmbara secular book which deals with the life-cycle ritual of the Jain Śvetāmbara sect. Other than these, there are some other secular works too on Jain personal law, such as *Bhadrabāhu Saṃhitā* of **Bhadrabāhu** (ca. 8th – 15th century CE), *Vardhamānanīti* of **Amitagati** (ca. 1011 CE), *Jina Saṃhitā* of **Vasunandi Indranandi** (10th Century CE) and *Traivarṇikācāra* of **Somasena** (1160 CE).

As according to Jain tradition quarrels lead to passionate and hostile feeling, and Jainism aims at the suppression and eradication of these, chiefly of anger (*krodha*), pride (*māna*), deceit (*māya*) and greed (*lobha*), as they imprison the soul in matter and retard its evolution on to freedom and liberation from misery (*Bhadrabāhu Saṃhitā*, *Dāyabhāga* 2-3). Thus Bhadrabāhu, the author or compiler of these śloka, flourished about 340 BCE, at least 365 BCE (because he was the last of the Śrutakevalin). This book consists of 12,000 śloka. Along with the various subjects, one of the chapters of this book surprisingly deals with the law of inheritance. It helps to determine quarrels among members of the same family. The pioneering *Bhadrabāhu Saṃhitā* was cited by all later texts, even by treatises of Śvetāmbara authors such as the *Arhannīti* of Hemācāryā.

The books *Vardhamānanīti* and the *Jina Saṃhitā* are not available in its complete form. The previous one was written in Sanskrit and the latter one was in Prakṛt. Both the books deal with the law of inheritance. *Traivarnīkācāra*, in contrast, is an interesting book of the Jains, and this is an exceptional too, because, this book particularly deals with each and every custom, which are necessary for the Traivarnas — three upper castes *viz.* the Brāhmaṇa, the Kṣatriya and the Vaiśya. In this context, this book also deals with some of the special rules and regulation for the ascetics. Even the book time to time has recorded various rules relating to the Śūdras also.

Other than these treatises *Arhannīti* of Hemācārya (12th – 14th century CE) is another important and rare Jain Śvetāmbara work on statecraft along with the Jain personal law. The text provides us a good deal of additional information of a type not found in the *dharmaśāstra*, and this is a contribution to Indian legal history in its own right (like rights of widow to inherit etc.).

Most of these works invariably draw inspirations from the Brāhmical law books such as Manu and others, but these texts have also enclosed various original notions like the right of widow to inherit or to adopt a son etc. Some of the nationalist Jain barristers and orthodox Jain elites have used all of these aforesaid Jain texts to create a new set of laws for the Jains at the second decade of the 20th century. However, they are not adequately successful in making the Jain religion as an independent religion with the help of those newly prepared Jain law. They often fall back on the well-entrenched Hindu law to explain the strength and validity of the well accepted customs of the Jain. Some nationalist Jains are not even able to resolve issues concerning how all the Jains would be governed by one single set of laws, where some of their local traditions (*deśācāra*) and family customs (*kulācāra*) vary from one place to another.

At this juncture, I would like to point out some of the unique features of the Jain Personal Law according to the Jain Legal scriptures.

Law of Adoption

- According to the Hindu *Dharmaśāstric* Law it is well-known that the obligation to procreate is the central idea to the Brāhmaṇical theology of religious life, only next in importance

to sacrifice. In his final instruction, the teacher reminds the pupil, who has completed his Vedic studies and is about to assume the responsibility of adulthood of this obligation: “Speak the truth. Follow the Law (*dharma*). Do not neglect the daily Vedic recitation. Bring a generous gift for the teacher, and then do not *cut off* the line of progeny (*Taittirīya Upaniṣad* 01/11/01).” According to the theory of three debts, to have a son is considered a ‘must’ for every member of the Brāhmaṇical community. Therefore, just like marriage, “to have a son” is not only a secular act for them. The son is believed to be a rescuer of his father from the hell, called *put*, that is why the son is called *putra* in Sanskrit. As a result, when a man is not able to procreate by himself, according to the scripture, he is allowed to adopt to secure his own funeral and transcendental rites as well. Predominantly, adoption is considered a sacramental act with a secular purpose. After the codification of Hindu Law, there has been an acute controversy not only among the writers, but also among the judges, whether the act of adoption is predominantly secular or religious in nature.⁵ Some of the judges still insist that the object of adoption is two-fold – to assure one’s funeral rites and to preserve the continuance of one’s lineage.⁶ Under the Dharmaśāstric Law (from where Hindu Law was codified), there were many rules relating to adoption which could be supported only on the basis of the fact that the act of adoption was nothing but a religious reform. In case of adoption, for instance, the present law does not feel to allow a man for adopting a son, who already had the same, as it is well-known that the cause behind this adoption law was for the spiritual gain merely. Therefore, if the spiritual purpose is solved having a single son (biological or adopted), law does not allow to adopt another.

- According to the Jaina Law to have a son is not an obligatory duty of the Jaina laity to secure his own funeral and transcendental rites. Bhadrabāhu does not support the Dharmaśāstric theology that the men by having sons become religiously meritorious; and by being sonless is considered to be a sinful.

5 See Mayne Hindu Law and Usage, (11th Ed., pp 184-88)

6 Inder Singh vs. Kartar Singh, 1966 Punj 258

According to him many people in this world are seen in a low position and begging for gains; and sonless *Tirthaṅkaras* (the Jaina men-god) on the other hand, are found to attain the Five Great Acquisitions,⁷ their lotus-feet are worshiped by the god of gods, and they are possessed of insight into the three worlds. Therefore, according to the Jaina personal law to have a son is not a religious act at all. Therefore, adopting more than one son would not be invalid according to the Law.⁸

- According to the Hindu Law a valid adoption cannot be undone. Jaina Law on the other hand, the parents have a provision to expel the adopted son from the house, if the adopted son goes beyond control, or opposed to religion, and does not reform. The King then cannot listen to any petition of his rights by the expelled one. He shall then have no rights left relating to the inheritance. If the adopted son behaves affectionately towards the parents and is obedient to them then he is regarded equal to the natural son.⁹
- According to Hindu law, a woman alone was not entitled to take adoption without the permission of her husband; therefore, the widow was not entitled to take adoption, as the permission of her deceased husband could not be possible. On the other hand, Jaina Law allows a widow of a deceased to adopt. No authority or consent is necessary for adoption by a widow. If there be two-widows, the elder of them may adopt a son without the consent of the younger. The point is that the person in possession of the estate as an heir alone is entitled to take a son in adoption.¹⁰

Law of Inheritance

- Unlike the Hindu law, the Jaina law recommends partition

7 The pañcakalyāna's are: Human Conception (garbha), Human Birth (janma), Austerities (tapa), Omniscience (kevala jñāna) and Salvation (mokṣa).

8 पुत्रेण स्यात्पुण्यवत्त्वमपुत्रः पापयुग्भवेत् । पुलवन्तोऽत्र दृश्यन्ते पामराः कणयाचकाः ॥ दृष्टास्तीर्थकृतोऽपुत्रा पञ्चकल्याणभागिनः । देवेन्द्रपूज्यपादाब्जा लोकत्रयविलोकिनः ॥ — (Bhadrabāhusamhitā 8 - 9)

9 दत्तकः प्रतिकूलः स्यात् पितृभ्यां प्राग्मृदुक्तिकः । बोधयेत्तं पुनर्दर्पात् तादृशो जनकस्त्वरम् ॥ तत्पिलादीन् तदुद्धान्तं ज्ञापयित्वा प्रबोधयेत् । भूयोऽपि तादृशश्चैव बन्धुभूपाधिकारिणाम् ॥ आज्ञामादाय गृहतो निष्कास्यो ह्यभकस्त्वरम् । न तन्नियोगं भूपाद्याः शुण्वन्ति हि कदाचनः ॥ — (Bhadrabāhusamhitā , 52-4)

10 ग्राह्यः सद्गौलजः पुत्रो भर्ता इव कुलस्त्रिया । भर्तृस्थाने नियोक्तव्यो न श्वश्चा स्वपतेः पदे ॥ — (Bhadrabāhusamhitā 35)

because it leads to the increase of *dharmā* (virtue), and enables every brother separately to accumulate merit for himself.¹¹

According to Jaina Law, after the death of the father, if a partition takes place, the mother is entitled to a share equal to that of the sons.¹² As a matter of fact, it is laid down that she should receive a little more than a share so that she may be able to maintain the dignity and position of the family. *Dharmaśāstra* has no such provision relating to the extra-share for the wife of the deceased owner of the property.

The Ascetic's share

- If before partition a person has renounced the world, then at the time of partition *Strīdhana* will be left out of account and the shares will be calculated as if he were present, and his share will be given to his wife.¹³
- If he has left (only) a son he will naturally take the place of his father. If a person dies without marrying, or becomes a *Sādhu*, his share will be taken by his brother and nephew according to law.¹⁴
- According to *Bhadrabāhu Saṃhitā* the sister is also entitled to a share. But probably the sister of this śloka is only the unmarried sister provide for whose marriage is the pious obligation of the brothers.¹⁵

Now I would like to cite some of the law suits decided during the colonial rule where the existence and the authority of Jaina Law as distinct from Hindu Law were asserted.

- An old case is *Govinda Nath Ray v. Gulab Chand* (1833), 5 Sel. Rep., S. D. A., Cal. 276. Here Jaina law triumphed (obtain victory). It was held that Jaina widow can adopt a son, without

11 यद्यपि भ्रातृणामेकचित्तत्वं पुण्यप्रभावस्तथापि । धर्मवृद्धये पृथग्भवनमपि योज्यम् । मूनीनामाहारदानादिना सर्वेषां पुण्यभागित्वात् । भोगभूमिजन्मरूपफलप्राप्तिः स्यात्तदेवाह । विभक्ता भ्रातरो भिन्नास्तिष्ठन्तु सपरिच्छदाः । दानपूजादिना पुण्यं वृद्धिः संजायतेतराम् ॥ — (*Bhadrabāhusaṃhitā* , 11)

12 सहोदरैर्निजाम्बाया भागस्सम उदाहृतः । साधिको व्यवहारार्थं मृतौ सर्वैशभागिनः ॥ — (*Bhadrabāhusaṃhitā* , 21); She is entitled to a slightly large share for meeting the ordinary social expenses (*vyavahārārtha*). And on her death, all share it.

13 मुक्त्युपायोद्यतश्चैकोऽविभक्तेषु च भ्रातृषु । स्त्रीधनं तु परित्यज्य विभजेरन् समं धनम् ॥ । — (*Bhadrabāhusaṃhitā* , 84); पारिव्रज्या गृहीतैकेनाविभक्तेषु बन्धुषु । विभागकाले तद्भागं तत्पत्नी लातुमर्हति ॥ — (*Arhannīti*, 90)

14 पुत्रवर्जितः कोऽपि मृतः प्रब्रजितोऽथवा । सर्वे तद्भ्रातरस्तस्य गृहीयुस्तद्धनं समम् ॥ — (*Arhannīti*, 91)

15 जाते विभागे बहुषु पुत्रेष्वेको मृतो यदि । विभजेरन् समं रिक्थं सभगिन्यः सहोदराः ॥ — (*Bhadrabāhusaṃhitā* , 106); The sister is given a share by way of a provision for her marriage, for she is not an heir.

the sanction of her husband. This was a Murshidabad case, and the decision was apparently based upon the *vyāvasthā* of the Pandits who said: “According to Jaina Shastras a sonless widow may adopt a son, just as may her husband, for the performance of rites. The sanction of her husband or the direction of the *yatis* or priests is not essential.”

- In 1863, a case was fought in Shahabad (Bihār), *sub nomine Chandan Koer v. Padmanath Koer*. In this, a Jaina joint brother succeeded by survivorship to his brother. The widow of the deceased brother claimed to succeed by Jaina custom. The case was compromised.
- In 1878, in *Sheo Sing Rai B. Dakho*, 1 A. 688, a Meerut case, a sonless Jaina widow was held to take “an absolute interest at least in the self-acquired property of her husband or his kinsmen. It was held that she could validly adopt a daughter’s son. This was certainly a triumph of Jaina Law, as according to Hindu Law this kind of Adoption is not valid.

In the concluding section, I would like to say that I have tried to point out the legal identities of the Jains with the help of their own legal texts and the medieval Jain literature. Consequently, I have pointed out the similarities and the dissimilarities lie down between the Jain law and the law of Brahmanical *dharmaśāstras*. Such a critical comparative study, on the basis of textual as well as historical evidences, between the Hindu and the Jaina law has not yet been done before. The possible reason might be that the Jain legal texts has recorded various directives relating to the monastic as well as civil jurisprudence¹⁶ which is sometime very much alike to the Hindu *dharmaśāstric* texts. The scholars, for that reason, always keep away from studying the Jain legal literatures, which remain various original ideas too. Pertinent questions, therefore, are to be needed to be addressed in this connection (i) Is the flavor of Brāhmanism, which pervades the Jain law, a matter of substance, or of accident? (ii) Which one of these two legal systems is more ancient? (iii) Why have not the Jains developed a full-fledged legal

¹⁶ I have not yet located the criminal jurisprudence recorded into the Jaina legal texts. It may also be possible that the Jains might not have developed the criminal laws, because of its completely secular identity, as we found into the Hindu legal texts.

system like the Hindus? The Jain law was originally a part of what is known as the *Upāsakādhyāyāna Aṅga*, which is now lost. The study of Jain law, for that reason, will also help to presume at least some of the relevant portions of the lost *Upāsakādhyāyāna Aṅga*. To the best of my knowledge, study of Jaina Personal Law, will both enrich and expand our existing knowledge of Indian legal chronicles, unobserved by the earlier scholars.

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